

IMPROVED MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUES FOR THIN FILAMENT-WOUND CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

Thin filament-wound cylinders can be produced from many different materials and techniques. The objective of this study was to improve the quality of thin filament-wound cylinders manufactured with prepregged tows. Three curing techniques were examined during this study: those cured in a convection oven, autoclave cured, and cylinders cured with shrink tape. Room and elevated-temperature winding were also examined. Since one of the most demanding structural applications for thin filament-wound cylinders is compressive buckling, geometric imperfection measurements and visual examination were used to assess cylinder quality.

Keywords: filament winding, composites manufacture, imperfections, buckling

INTRODUCTION

With the increased use of composite materials for structural applications, there is an incentive to develop high-quality, cost-effective manufacturing procedures. One such application is thin cylinders subjected to compressive buckling loads. Performance of these structures is particularly dependent on the level of geometric imperfections in the shell [1,2]. Cylinders fabricated by hand from unidirectional prepregged plies have unparalleled quality; however, they are very time consuming and costly to produce in large numbers. Automated manufacturing procedures, such as filament winding and braiding, can be used to consistently produce structures with high quality.

Filament-wound cylinders can be produced with many different materials and combinations of winding and curing techniques. The most common of these manufacturing techniques is called wet winding. During wet winding a liquid matrix material is mixed with dry fibers as the structure is being wound. Low viscosity thermosetting resins and solutions of thermoplastic polymers and solvents are commonly wet wound. The reinforcing fibers and matrix can also be mixed before winding in the form of preimpregnated strands or tapes, commingled yarns, or powder coated fibers. Prepregged materials are easier and safer to use since no liquid resin or solvent is used; however, the added cost of the prepregging operation is a disadvantage of this technique.

The objective of this study was to improve the quality of thin filament-wound cylinders, wound with prepregged tows, for use in compressive buckling applications. Room and elevated-temperature winding in conjunction with oven, autoclave, and shrink-tape curing techniques were evaluated on the basis of visual, microstructural, and geometric quality.

MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUES

Each cylinder manufactured during this study was wound with Amoco T650-35/1908 graphite/epoxy prepreg tow on either 57 or 152-mm. diameter mandrels of either aluminum or steel. A McClean-Anderson three-axis filament winder was used to perform the winding and an American Sahn bi-directional tensioner was used to maintain a uniform tension. Various combinations of mandrel diameter, winding angle, bandwidth, and dwell angle, were used during this study.

Winding at an elevated temperature was accomplished by employing an infrared heater attached to the payout eye of the filament winder, as shown in Figure 1. The heater was adjusted so that the resin visibly flowed as the tow was wound on the mandrel. The amount of heat applied depended on the winding angle of the layer, helical or circumferential, and the rate of winding. In addition to improving the consolidation of each layer, the flowing resin displaces air and fills in depressions around gaps, twists, and fiber crossovers, similar to the resin flow that occurs during wet winding. The heat was carefully regulated since an elevated winding temperature can cause the epoxy to cure prematurely.

Figure 1. Infrared heater location used for elevated-temperature winding.

A typical wet wound part is cured by slowly rotating the mandrel and cylinder in a convection oven. To form a basis of comparison, a forced convection oven was used to cure a $[90/\pm 30/\pm 30/90]$ cylinder filament wound with prepregged tow on a 57-mm. diameter mandrel. The void content and degree of consolidation are primarily dependent on the winding tension where increased tension typically results in smaller and fewer voids.

The most common technique for producing high quality flat laminates is to use a vacuum bagging scheme in conjunction with an autoclave. Rather than relying on fiber tension for consolidation and resin flow, autoclave curing techniques use externally applied pressures to improve the quality of the composite. For large structures, this curing technique increases costs significantly since large quantities of consumable vacuum bagging supplies are required along with expenses associated with the autoclave. Two $[90/\pm 30/\pm 30/90]$ cylinders were wound, covered with vacuum bagging materials, one each in no-resin-bleed and resin-bleed configurations, and then cured in a Baron model BAC-37 computer-controlled autoclave at 586 MPa. external pressure and -97 MPa in the vacuum bag.

Another technique that can be used to apply external pressure to filament-wound cylinders involves wrapping the cylinder in high-temperature shrink tape before cure. The cylinder is then placed in a normal convection oven and, as the temperature rises, the tape shrinks and consolidates the composite. Cylinders manufactured with this technique were first covered with 51-mm. wide strips of porous, fiberglass-reinforced, release cloth by winding the cloth by hand with moderate tension to prevent wrinkles, as shown schematically in Figure 2. Shrink tape was then wound over the release cloth with hand tension. The same number of layers of release cloth and shrink tape were applied at each location to prevent thickness variations due to the applied mechanical pressure from the shrink tape. Although porous release cloth was used, little resin was removed from the cylinder during cure.

since several layers of non-porous shrink tape were applied. Table 1 contains the winding and curing parameters investigated for each specimen for this portion of the study.

Figure 2. Shrink tape curing technique showing the placement of porous release cloth and shrink tape.

Table 1. Selected winding and curing parameters used to manufacture $[90/\pm 30/\pm 30/90]$ filament-wound cylinders.

Manufacturing Technique	Winding Tension (N)	Winding Temperature	Pressurization	Cure Technique
I	9	Room	None	Oven
II	9	Room	Autoclave	Bleed
III	9	Room	Autoclave	No-Bleed
IV	9	Room	Shrink Tape	Oven
V	22	Elevated	None	Oven
VI	22	Elevated	Shrink Tape	Oven

QUALITY ASSESSMENT

The quality of composite structures is difficult to quantify. Depending on the specific application, the quality may be governed by the appearance, microstructure, void content, geometry, stiffness, strength, damage tolerance, or any combination of these parameters. When thin-cylindrical cylinders are subjected to axial compression, the critical quality issues are the extent of material and geometric imperfections [3]. Consequently, the thickness of the shell was measured at many points, and the geometry of the actual cylinder was compared to a mathematically perfect cylinder. Also, cylinders manufactured for this study were examined visually at both macro and microscopic levels. Visual examination of each cylinder was made to locate gross errors in the winding or curing such as: tow twisting, gaps in the layer coverage, and the effects of nonuniform cure pressure. Sections of cylinder were also machined, mounted in a room-temperature curing epoxy, polished, and examined with a light microscope to determine the location, amount, and size of the voids, and the distribution of resin and fibers.

To measure the thickness distribution, the method of Claus [4] was used. This technique involved placing the cylinders on the same mandrel on which they were wound and installing the mandrel in the filament-winder. A spring loaded, Linear Variable Displacement Transformer (LVDT, Lucas Schaevitz model PCA-116) was fitted with a 1.6-mm. diameter spherical contact tip and mounted to the payout eye. The small diameter contact tip was used so that local imperfections, such as wrinkles in the release cloth and twists in the prepreg tow, could be measured. The filament winder was programmed to move the LVDT across the cylinder in a systematic fashion. This technique assumes intimate contact between the cylinder and mandrel and cannot be used with cylinders with more than a few plies.

The geometric imperfections were measured after the cylinders were affixed to the end plates used for compression testing, as reported by Claus [4]. The cylinders were placed on a machinist's turntable with the aid of an adapter, and the spring-loaded LVDT was mounted to measure lateral displacement as the cylinder was rotated. Data measured in this fashion was compared to a mathematical model of a perfect cylinder similar to the work of Arbocz [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When filament-wound cylinders were cured in a convection oven without the use of external compaction pressure, the resulting laminate was typically quite thick, although uniform in the circumferential direction. The exterior surface of the shell contains imperfections due to misalignment and twisting of the tow during winding. The laminate contains many large voids throughout the layers, as shown in Figure 3a. The severity of each of these problems can be attributed to low consolidation pressure during manufacture, since, quality depends on fiber tension only with this technique. Increasing the tension could improve the quality of the cylinder; however, to obtain acceptable quality levels, very high tensions would be required. When the tow is heated during winding, a substantial improvement in consolidation and void content was observed, as shown in Figure 3b. Unlike the cold-wound cylinder, when this specimen was cured, substantial resin flow was observed. Resin forced to the surface during winding and the increased fiber tension, 9 N and 22 N for the heated and unheated cylinders respectively, caused the increased resin flow. Drips and sag marks also formed during cure. Cylinder rotation during cure would eliminate these defects; however, a thick, resin rich layer on the outside surface would still result.

a) manufacturing technique I

b) manufacturing technique II

Figure 3. Photomicrographs of typical cross sections of $[90/\pm 30/\pm 30/90]$ filament-wound cylinders manufactured without external compaction pressure.

When cylinders were manufactured with an autoclave, the laminates contained few voids and were well consolidated. However, when external pressure was applied during cure, the breather and bleeder layers were radially compressed and wrinkled. The wrinkles were transferred to the filament-wound cylinder and formed ridges in the cured structure, as shown in Figure 4a. These wrinkles constitute a serious defect, especially when the material is loaded in compression, since they contain fibers. When the no-bleed bagging configuration was used, and the breather was tightly wound over the composite, wrinkles also developed, as shown in Figure 4b. The inner 90° layer is not visible in Figure 4b because the photomicrographic specimen was machined at gap in the layer. The wrinkles in this cylinder are much less prominent than the other autoclaved cylinder. Restricting the resin flow resulted in a visible difference in the fiber-volume content and degree of consolidation.

When high-temperature shrink tape was used to apply pressure, the overall appearance of the shell was much better than with both previous methods. Outer surface wrinkles were minimized by winding the porous release cloth uniformly and with sufficient tension, and since the shrink tape aids in transverse motion of fibers and resin. Numerous voids are still present when this technique is combined with room-temperature winding, as shown in Figure 5a; however, the size of individual voids and their number is less than when no shrink tape is used (see Figure 3a). Heated winding

a) manufacturing technique III

b) manufacturing technique IV

Figure 4. Photomicrographs of typical cross sections of $[90/\pm 30/\pm 30/90]$ filament-wound cylinders manufactured in an autoclave.

further improved the void content and exterior surface smoothness of cylinders manufactured with the shrink tape technique, as shown in Figure 5b. These cylinders possess the best combination of void size, number of voids, and exterior surface finish based on visual quality assessment.

a) manufacturing technique V

b) manufacturing technique VI

Figure 5. Photomicrographs of typical cross sections of $[90/\pm 30/\pm 30/90]$ filament-wound cylinders manufactured with high-temperature shrink tape.

Visual methods of quality assessment are fast and inexpensive, yet difficult to quantify. Measurement of the thickness distributions of $[\pm 30]$ cylinders, manufactured with Technique IV (see Table 1), was used to help quantify the quality of filament-wound cylinders. This technique is very

sensitive to the local imperfections, as shown in Figure 6. The most common causes of thickness variations observed during this study were either misplaced tows, inconsistent rotation of the payout eye, or twisting of the prepregged tow before contact with the mandrel. Even when shrink tape was used, the pressure exerted on the composite was often insufficient to completely smooth the surface. Figure 7 contains the thickness distributions of a a) visually poor quality cylinder, and a b) high quality cylinder. Both specimens were wound at room temperature with the same winding parameters and cured with the shrink tape technique; however, the effects of tow twisting and fiber misalignments are readily apparent.

Figure 6. Local detail of measured thickness distribution and photograph of actual surface features.

Residual thermal stresses, which arise due to the antisymmetry of the helically-wound layers, can result in large geometric imperfections. Since the compression-twisting coupling terms of these laminates are non-zero, thin cylinders with these layers may have substantial geometric imperfections

Figure 7. Typical thickness distributions of cold wound, shrink-tape cured $[\pm 30]$ filament-wound cylinders with a) poor visual quality, and b) good visual quality.

before loading. The actual deformed shape of the cylinder is dependent on the specific winding pattern and the stresses induced by potting the cylinder in the end fixtures. Tennyson et al. [6] has suggested that measurements of global cylinder geometry be incorporated into a design criterion for cylinders subjected to axial compression.

Figure 8 contains the plots of the imperfection amplitude, defined as the difference between the actual surface of the cylinder and a mathematically perfect cylinder, for four room-temperature wound, shrink-tape cured, $[\pm 30]$ cylinders and the root-mean-square of the imperfection amplitude computed over the entire surface, α_{rms} . The large variations in amplitude, especially apparent near the ends of the cylinder, are also visible in the unpotted specimens. These imperfections differ dramatically from those reported by Chryssanthopoulos et al. [7] who investigated cylinders fabricated from unidirectional prepreg sheet by hand. Many of the local imperfections in the filament-wound cylinders are not apparent in their specimens; however, the large ridges, caused by overlapping the prepreg layers, are absent in filament-wound cylinders. As a quality criterion, the geometric measurements are very valuable due to the sensitivity of axial compression to these imperfections and the difficulty in detecting these imperfections by other non-destructive methods.

CONCLUSIONS

Substantial improvements in the quality of filament-wound cylinders can be achieved by correct choice of winding and curing parameters. Various combinations of cold and heated winding, bleed and no-bleed vacuum bagging, and shrink tape and non-pressurized cure schemes were evaluated based on the visual appearance, microstructure, thickness distribution, and geometric deviations. Winding the material at an elevated temperature to promote resin flow and in-situ consolidation, then curing the cylinder with multiple layers of high-temperature shrink tape, produces a cylinder with a low void content, good distribution of fibers and resin, and a smooth exterior surface. The local imperfections observed in cylinders manufactured by hand from unidirectional prepreg, can be eliminated in filament-wound cylinders at the expense of geometric accuracy.

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Figure 8. Typical imperfection amplitudes of room-temperature wound, shrink-tape cured filament-wound cylinders with various imperfection amplitudes and geometric shapes.

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